

Assessing Privacy Practices on Ontario Municipal Websites

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Abstract—The sharing of personal data on government websites is a major concern of daily users. The existing regulations do not allow for the collection and sharing of personal data. This study investigates the privacy practices of 444 municipal websites across Ontario, Canada, focusing on compliance with relevant data protection regulations and the extent of third-party data sharing. In particular, we examine the issues in line with Canadian standards, the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA), the Canadian Privacy Act (CPA), and the Municipal Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (MFIPPA). We perform network traffic analysis, and apply a combination of privacy policies. Our findings uncover substantial gaps in privacy practices, including insufficient transparency, inadequate user-consent mechanisms, and pervasive third-party data sharing. The results of our study highlight an urgent need for the enhancement of privacy measures on government municipal websites to protect the personal data of users and for the implementation of practices that comply with local and international privacy laws, such as PIPEDA, CPA, MFIPPA, and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The study provides actionable recommendations aimed at strengthening data protection and restoring public trust in digital municipal services.

Index Terms—Municipal Website, Data Privacy and Security, Third-Party Data Sharing, Network Traffic Analysis, Data Transparency, Personal Data.

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital transformation of municipal services has become a cornerstone of modern governance, offering citizens and international users convenient access to information and essential services. However, this shift towards digital platforms has raised significant concerns regarding privacy, particularly the leakage of personal data to third parties without user consent. Municipal websites often serve as the primary interface between local governments and their user base. They increasingly incorporate third-party services such as analytics tools,

social media plugins, and advertising networks. While these services enhance functionality, they also introduce potential privacy risks by transmitting sensitive personal data to external entities, making these platforms vulnerable to data breaches, unauthorized access, and third-party tracking.

A growing body of research has highlighted the vulnerabilities associated with third-party data sharing on public sector websites. Studies have revealed that many municipal websites around the globe fail to adequately protect personal data, leading to unauthorized sharing with third parties, often without the knowledge or consent of the users [1], [2]. These practices not only undermine public trust, but also expose municipalities to potential legal liabilities, particularly in regions with stringent data protection regulations. For example, in the European Union (EU), the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) imposes strict requirements on how personal data must be handled, emphasizing that consent must be “freely given”, specific, informed, and unambiguous. Similarly, in Canada, the Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA) mandates that organizations obtain meaningful consent before collecting, using, or disclosing personal information.

Ontario, a province in Canada, recognized for its progressive adoption of digital services, has seen a rapid expansion in the use of municipal websites to serve its diverse population. This trend is particularly evident in the hierarchical adoption of e-governance tools, where larger municipalities within the province are leading the way in implementing advanced digital services to enhance public access and engagement [3]. While this digital shift has enhanced the efficiency and accessibility of public services, it has also underscored the vulnerabilities associated with the collection and management of personal data. The Municipal Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (MFIPPA), alongside other regulations such as PIPEDA and the GDPR for EU citizens, establishes the legal framework for data protection. However, the inconsistent

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implementation and enforcement of these regulations across municipal websites have resulted in varying levels of compliance and exposure to privacy risks.

Recent reports have also highlighted the growing concern of cyber threats, where hackers exploit legitimate websites by injecting malicious scripts to deliver malware to unsuspecting visitors [4]. This tactic is particularly alarming for municipal websites, which often rely on third-party services, as these external scripts and plugins can become vulnerable entry points for cybercriminals. On a user's first visit, the website's code collects sensitive information, such as device details, IP addresses, user-agents, and locations, which is then transmitted to a specified domain via an HTTP request. This process, especially when conducted without user consent or awareness, poses significant privacy and security risks. There is an urgent need for how municipal websites must enhance both their security measures and transparency when handling personal data, especially while integrating third-party services, to avoid becoming channels for data leaks or spreading malware.

This paper investigates the privacy practices of municipal websites across Ontario, focusing on their compliance with relevant data protection regulations and the prevalence of third-party data sharing. By analyzing the network traffic of the websites, the study identifies patterns of data sharing with third-party services, evaluates the transparency and accessibility of privacy policies, and examines the effectiveness of user consent mechanisms. The research uncovers significant gaps in adherence to regulations, including issues of insufficient transparency, inadequate user consent processes, and widespread third-party data sharing often conducted without user knowledge or consent. These findings underscore the critical need for enhanced privacy practices on municipal websites, both to meet legal obligations and to maintain trust and credibility among both local and international users.

II. LEGAL FRAMEWORKS GOVERNING PRIVACY

There are several legal frameworks governing the privacy that are related to this study. We briefly review them here.

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), enforced in the European Union since May 2018, is one of the most comprehensive privacy and security laws in the world [5]. It applies to any organization, regardless of location, that processes the personal data of EU residents. The GDPR is built on several key principles, including the requirement that personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently.

The Personal Information Protection and Electronic Documents Act (PIPEDA) is Canada's federal privacy law for private-sector organizations. It governs how businesses collect, use, and disclose personal information in the course of commercial activities. PIPEDA applies to organizations across Canada, except in provinces that have enacted substantially similar legislation.

The Municipal Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (MFIPPA) is Ontario's legislation that applies to municipal governments and local institutions, such as

school boards, public utilities, and transit authorities. MFIPPA provides the public with a right to access records held by these institutions while also protecting individuals' privacy by setting rules for the collection, use, and disclosure of personal information.

The **Canadian Privacy Act** is a federal law that governs how personal information is handled by government institutions. This Act ensures that government institutions, including municipal entities when applicable, collect, use, and disclose personal information in a manner that respects individuals' privacy rights.

Although the Privacy Act primarily applies to federal institutions, its principles are relevant to municipal websites, especially when federal programs or services are integrated into local government websites. The Privacy Act's focus on transparency, data minimization, and individual rights complements the privacy protection measures outlined in other legislation such as PIPEDA and MFIPPA. Municipalities must ensure that their digital practices align with these principles to safeguard the personal information of all users.

These privacy laws introduce additional layers of complexity, particularly in terms of compliance with varying data protection laws. For instance, visitors from the European Union (EU) are protected under the GDPR, which imposes strict requirements on how their data can be collected, stored, and shared. Municipalities must therefore ensure that their websites are not only compliant with local privacy regulations, such as the MFIPPA and PIPEDA, but also with international laws like the GDPR. Failure to adequately protect the privacy of international users could lead to significant legal and reputational risks, particularly in a globalized world where data protection laws are increasingly stringent and enforcement actions are more common.

III. RECENT PROGRESS IN RELATED RESEARCH

The growing dependence on online services has raised significant concerns about privacy, especially regarding the data leaks to the third-parties on local government websites. Authors of the study in [6] conducted an early and influential evaluation in this field, examining municipal websites worldwide over time [6]. Their research systematically evaluated aspects such as security, user-friendliness, content quality, available services, and citizen engagement. Subsequent research has expanded their findings, demonstrating a global concern regarding privacy and data management practices across various municipalities and sectors. For example, Finnish studies by Rauti et al. [1] [2] uncovered significant privacy vulnerabilities in municipal websites, while Dutch research by Beldad, De Jong, and Stehouder [7] explored how these sites handle personal data and its impact on trust. In the USA, studies by Wilson and Cong [8], Schuele [9], and Goodspeed [10] examined open data initiatives and privacy protections, revealing gaps and barriers. Lev-On and Steinfeld [11] in Israel, Serrano-Cinca and Muñoz-Soro [12] in Spain, and Król and Zdonek [13] in Poland further analyzed digital privacy and accessibility issues on municipal websites. Additionally,

several studies in Canada [14] [15] [16] emphasized the importance of addressing these issues in the public sector.

The methodologies employed in these studies demonstrate a diverse set of approaches for investigating digital privacy concerns and open data initiatives in municipal contexts. Rauti et al. [1] [2] utilized network traffic analysis to identify data leaks on Finnish municipal websites, particularly focusing on the leakage of user-visited URLs and search terms to third parties without user consent. Beldad et al. [7] in the Netherlands conducted comprehensive surveys to assess the extent and nature of privacy statements and third-party tracking on municipal websites. In the USA, Wilson and Cong used qualitative methods, including semi-structured interviews with stakeholders, while Schuele used content analysis to evaluate privacy policy statements [9], and Goodspeed performed public records requests and surveys to assess GIS data accessibility in Massachusetts municipalities [10]. Canadian studies involved interviews, policy document analysis, and descriptive analysis to evaluate open data programs and smart city initiatives [14] [15] [16].

In this study, we aim to address the privacy challenges associated with third-party data breaches on municipal websites in Ontario, underscoring the critical importance of data security as municipalities increasingly adopt digital platforms. While similar studies have been conducted in various parts of the world, there is a noticeable gap in research focused on the Canadian context, particularly in Ontario. By examining Ontario's municipal websites, this study aims to uncover potential privacy risks and evaluate the effectiveness of existing protective measures.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research uses a comprehensive methodological approach, integrating both detailed analysis and systematic evaluation to assess the privacy policies and network traffic of municipal websites. The primary goal was to systematically identify, assess, and validate third-party data leaks and associated privacy issues. The methodology began with the selection of Ontario municipal websites, which formed the foundation for the entire study. This selection was made to ensure relevance to a specific region, allowing for a more focused and manageable dataset. The list of municipal websites was sourced from the official Ontario government repository [17], encompassing all 444 municipal websites in Ontario. This broad selection provided a thorough overview of privacy practices across municipalities of varying sizes and locations.

Following the selection, the research process was divided into the following: **a) Privacy policy evaluation**, which assessed compliance with relevant data protection regulations; **b) Network traffic analysis**, which examined the extent of third-party data sharing on these websites. The flowchart in 1 highlights the key decision points and outcomes.

A. Privacy Evaluation

Each website was manually examined to determine the presence and adequacy of privacy policies and consent mechanisms.

The evaluation framework was based on compliance with relevant privacy regulations, including MFIPPA, PIPEDA, the Canadian Privacy Act, and GDPR.

- **Display of Privacy Policy or Consent Banner:** Websites were evaluated/assessed to determine/check if a privacy policy or consent banner was prominently displayed upon the first user interaction. Evaluating this presence provided initial insights into privacy practices, as well as maintaining transparency with users. The presence or absence of these elements was recorded for further analysis.
- **User Consent Options:** For websites with privacy policies or consent banners, further evaluation focused on the types of consent options available to users:
 - **Accept:** Users could accept all consent and data-sharing terms.
 - **Reject:** Users were given the option to reject non-essential consent. Under this option, it was critical to assess whether data was still shared with third parties despite user rejection.
 - **Unconditional Consent:** This option evaluated instances where websites displayed a consent banner but only provided an "Accept" button without any option for users to reject or customize the types of consent or data-sharing practices. This approach forces users to accept all consent in order to proceed, which may not fully align with best practices in privacy and data protection, as it limits user autonomy in managing their consent preferences.
- **Verification of Data Sharing:** In cases where users rejected consent, the research sought to verify if data was still being shared with third parties, which would represent a significant privacy breach.

B. Network Traffic Analysis

- i) This step involved analyzing the network traffic data on the municipal websites, filtering, and categorizing based on relevance to detect third-party data sharing. Additionally, this step involved verifying that the websites were actively in use, ensuring that the collected data accurately reflected the current state of the website's operations and privacy practices within the time frame of the analysis. The network traffic analysis was conducted in two stages, automated and then manually scanned inspection, to capture a comprehensive view of third-party data sharing practices.

- **Automated Analysis:** Automated scanning was conducted using a Python tool initially developed by Carlsson et al. [18], which was designed to efficiently capture and analyze network traffic data. This tool systematically scans any given website to analyze and identify third-party data sharing activities. For example, when running a test on a website, the tool generates a report to check if any search terms were transmitted to third-party domains. The report would

Fig. 1. Flowchart of Research Methodology and Outcomes

indicate whether any user details (e.g., search terms) were shared externally. The tool is versatile and can take screenshots of the websites being analyzed at the time the analysis is conducted, documenting any third-party data transmission that it detects. This functionality aids in providing evidence and record-keeping for any identified data sharing, further supporting the research findings and flagging outcomes for further manual inspection. The technical aspects of the tool have been elaborated in [18]. The tool was slightly modified to suit our research needs, ensuring it could effectively target the specific data-sharing activities relevant to this study, and input the findings in the spreadsheet directly.

- **Manual Inspection:** Tools like the Chrome DevTools network tab were used to manually inspect network traffic, capturing HTTP headers and third-party requests. This step was essential for understanding real-time data flows and identifying any suspicious activities that automated tools might overlook. Manual inspection involved a detailed and careful examination of websites, ensuring that significant findings were not missed by automated tools.
- ii) **Evaluation of Traffic Data:** In this stage, we sorted the results of the network analysis into three outcomes. This process provided valuable insights into the scope and nature of data exchange occurring on the municipal websites, which was crucial for evaluating privacy vulnerabilities. The information gathered from both automated and manual analyses was meticulously assessed to categorize the traffic data into the following groups:

- **Third-party Search Word Sharing:** Instances where search terms were shared with third parties were care-

fully documented, highlighting potential privacy risks. Additionally, any other details shared with third parties were also recorded.

- **Other Data Shared with Third Parties:** In cases where search terms were not shared, other types of data transmissions, such as user location, user identifiers, or browsing patterns, were recorded and analyzed.
- **No Third-party Sharing:** Websites that demonstrated compliance with privacy best practices by not sharing any data with third parties were noted.

V. RESULTS

In our study, 444 Ontario municipal websites were reviewed, 3 were not found, and 1 was not functioning, leaving 440 websites accessible for conducting the experiment and analysis.

A. Privacy Evaluation Results

The analysis of 440 municipal websites in Ontario revealed several key findings regarding the presence and implementation of privacy policies and consent mechanisms.

Out of the 440 municipal websites analyzed, 303 (68.9%) were found to have a privacy policy, while 137 (31.1%) did not have one. The fact that nearly one-third of websites lack privacy documentation, raises significant concerns about the management of personal data, indicating a lack of transparency and commitment to safeguarding user privacy. These gaps not only erode user trust, but could also leave municipalities vulnerable to legal issues, especially in regions with stringent data protection laws.

Notably, within the subset of websites that had a privacy policy, only 160 (52.81%) displayed the privacy policy embedded with a cookie policy upon the user's first visit. The remaining 143 (47.19%) websites, despite having a privacy policy, did not make this information immediately accessible to users during

their initial interactions with the site. This significant gap indicates potential issues with transparency and user awareness regarding data protection measures. These results underscore the pressing need for all websites to adopt privacy policies that ensure the responsible handling of personal data in accordance with applicable regulations.

Within the 160 municipal websites that displayed a privacy policy during the user’s initial interaction, a mere 7 (4.38%) allowed users the option to accept or reject the terms. Conversely, a large majority of 153 websites (95.62%) limited a user’s freedom and choice by presenting the privacy policy as a mandatory ‘agree-only’ option.

Furthermore, among the 7 websites that allowed users to reject the terms, 6 still transmitted personal data to third parties, leaving just 1 municipal website that fully honoured the rejection by not sharing any data. This prevalent practice of limiting user autonomy underscores significant concerns about the effectiveness of current data protection measures and the need for more balanced approaches to user consent management.

Specifically, Article 7 and Recital 32 of the GDPR [5] stress that consent must be obtained through a clear affirmative action, and that users must be informed of their right to withdraw consent at any time. Importantly, consent should not be bundled with other terms and conditions, meaning it cannot be a precondition for using a service unless the data processing is strictly necessary for the service itself. Also, Section 29(2) of MFIPPA mandates that institutions collecting personal information must inform individuals of the legal authority for the collection, the primary purpose of the collection, and provide contact details for an official who can address related inquiries. Compliance with this requirement varied among municipalities, with some adhering to it, while others did not. Table I shows the summary of the findings on Ontario Municipal Websites.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF PRIVACY POLICY AND DATA TRANSMISSION ANALYSIS OF
ONTARIO MUNICIPAL WEBSITES

Category	Count	Percentage
Websites Not Accessible	4	0.90%
Accessible Municipal Websites for Analysis	440	99.10%
Websites with Privacy Policy	303	68.9%
Websites without Privacy Policy	137	31.1%
Websites Displaying Privacy Policy on the first Visit	160	36.36% (of 440)
Websites Not Displaying Privacy Policy on the first Visit	143	32.5% (of 440)
Websites Allowing Accept/Reject Options	7	1.59% (of 440)
Websites with Agree-Only Option	153	34.77% (of 440)
Websites That Transmitted Data After Rejection	6	1.36% (of 440)
Websites That Did Not Transmit Data After Rejection	1	0.23% (of 440)

B. Network Analysis Results

The manual and automated analysis of the municipal websites was conducted within a defined time frame, beginning on

June 4, 2024, at 09:08:18 and concluding on July 10, 2024, at 18:55:20. This period was critical for ensuring that the data collected was current and accurately reflected the operational states of the websites during the analysis. The defined time frame also allowed for consistency and reliability, enabling manual verification to confirm the accuracy of the automated results during the network traffic analysis across the municipal websites.

During the analysis of 440 websites, it was found that 54 websites (12.3%) refrained from sharing personal data with third parties, either by not transmitting any data to external services or by not incorporating third-party services in the absence of a search function. However, a substantial proportion of 386 websites (87.7%) were observed to share users’ data with third-party services. Within this group of 386 websites, 352 (80.0%) specifically shared user search terms with third-party services, indicating a common reliance on external analytics or search functionalities.

In addition, from our analysis, 34 websites (7.7%) did not share search terms but still transmitted other personal data to third parties. Notably, among these 34 websites, 8 lacked a search box but still operated third-party services that shared user details. The breakdown underscores the prevalent use of third-party integrations across municipal websites, raising potential concerns regarding user privacy and the transparency of data practices. The widespread reliance on external services may pose significant privacy risks, particularly in the absence of clear consent mechanisms and adequate user control over data sharing.

The analysis of 440 accessible municipal websites revealed that Google was the most frequently detected third-party service. We define one instance as one case of data leak identified. Google appeared in 1123 instances, underscoring its widespread use for analytics and tracking purposes across numerous municipal websites. The total number of instances was over the websites since some websites may use multiple APIs. Other prominent third-party services included Cludo with 100 instances, Twitter with 93 instances, and Facebook with 56 instances, reflecting the integration of search functionalities and social media platforms into these municipal websites. The analysis also highlighted the diversity of third-party services employed, with some less commonly used tools like Monsido, which appeared 14 times, and Sitemprove, detected 19 times, indicating a focus on website accessibility and optimization by certain municipalities. Interestingly, some services, such as Tiktok, Pinterest, and Snapchat, were only detected once or twice, suggesting their use was limited to specific cases. In contrast, there were 54 instances where no third-party services were detected at all, suggesting that a subset of municipal websites may be opting out of third-party integrations, potentially to prioritize user privacy.

These findings underscore the pervasive nature of third-party service integration in municipal websites, with major tech companies like Google playing a dominant role. However, the presence of websites that do not utilize third-party services raises important considerations about the potential

for maintaining website functionality while safeguarding user privacy. The reliance on such a wide array of external services highlights the importance for municipalities to carefully evaluate the privacy implications associated with third-party data sharing and tracking.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study has revealed critical vulnerabilities in the privacy practices of municipal websites across Ontario, Canada, with significant implications for the protection of personal data and regulatory compliance. The analysis demonstrates that most of these websites engage in third-party data sharing, often without adequate transparency or user consent, raising serious concerns about the protection of personal information. Despite the existence of robust privacy laws such as GDPR, PIPEDA, and MFIPPA, the inconsistent application and enforcement of these regulations leave many municipal websites exposed to potential privacy breaches.

Based on our findings, we believe that there is an urgent need to focus on standard privacy policies that govern locally in Canada. Furthermore, the varying levels of responsiveness from municipalities in addressing identified privacy concerns highlight the challenges in achieving uniform privacy standards across the public sector. Our research was conducted only on municipal websites of selected regions, but in future studies we plan to increase the scope of our region to give a broader view of data privacy issues. Furthermore, we plan to perform comparative analyses using different automated tools and manual inspections, following existing standards to identify further findings.

VII. AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

A.D.A. conducted the experiments and drafted the manuscript, Y.Y., W.Z., S.R., and W.L. provided method design and guidance, Z.B. verified the results, all authors revised and reviewed the manuscript.

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